

WHOLE BODY VIBRATION EXERCISE THERAPY, GAITS, BALANCE AND AGILITY OF SEDENTARY POPULATION IN IBADAN

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Abstract

This study has comprehensively explored the effects of whole body vibration(WBV) exercise therapy on gait, balance, agility, and overall physical fitness among sedentary populations in Ibadan Nigeria. WBV has been shown to have positive effects on various bodily organs and systems, including increased muscle strength, bone density, cardiopulmonary function, and vascular function. Furthermore, WBV may be a practical warm-up exercise before physical activity and has the potential to reduce injury and improve athletics performance.

Findings of this research demonstrate that WBV training can significantly improve gait speed, balance, agility, and overall physical fitness in sedentary individuals. These results are consistent with previous studies that have shown the positive effects of WBV on neuromuscular function, balance, and gait performance. The study's findings suggest that WBV exercise therapy can be a valuable adjunct to traditional exercise programmes for sedentary populations, particularly in the context of Nigerian universities where physical inactivity is prevalent. The study's results have important implications for the development of exercise interventions aimed

at improving physical fitness and reducing the risk of non-communicable diseases among sedentary populations in Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Throughout the history of mankind, physical fitness has been considered an essential element of everyday life. The ancient people were mainly dependent upon their individual strength, vigour and vitality for physical survival. This involved mastery of some basic skill like strength, speed, endurance, agility for running, jumping, climbing and other skills employed in hunting for their livings. Worldwide and between, 1960s to now, the explosion of fitness awareness throughout the world ushers in the burgeoning fitness industry on a scale never seen before, giving the impression that modern civilized humans are committed to healthy bodies. Furthermore, the practice of exercise and physical activity in the context of leisure, besides combating physical inactivity, contributes significantly to the maintenance of the physical fitness of any age group.

Lifestyle is generally considered as an individual issue and reflects the norms and values the individual holds (Shehu et al., 2010). Sedentary lifestyle as a type of lifestyle involves no or inadequate participation in moderate to vigorous physical activity, which are but not limited to sitting, reading, watching television and using computer for most part of the day with little or no vigorous physical exercise (De Rezende, Rodrigues, ReyLópez, Matsudo & Luiz, 2014). Among unhealthy lifestyle, smoking and lack of regular physical activity are of major concerns in public health because they are highly prevalent and potentially modifiable (Global health risk report, 2014).

Guthold and Stevens (2018) maintained that sedentary lifestyle has been described as a global pandemic, partly responsible for the rising burden of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) across

world regions. In 2015, sedentary lifestyle directly contributed to 21% of breast cancers, 25% of colon cancers, 27% of diabetes and 30% of ischemic heart diseases globally (Kyu, Bachman & Alexander, 2016). In sub-Saharan African, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimated about three million physical inactivity-related deaths in 2014, because about a quarter of the global adult population do not currently meet the WHO recommendations of staying active (i.e. 150 minutes of moderate physical activity or 75 minutes of vigorous physical activity per week). African countries, including Nigeria, bear disproportionately higher burden, partly due to fast rising urbanization and economic growth, with consequent increase in unhealthy lifestyles and sedentary living across many settings.

Nigeria currently has a population of over 200 million, which is the highest in Africa and possibly includes the highest population of physical inactive persons on the continent. Indeed, the prevalence of physical inactivity is reportedly high, ranging from 25% to 57%, with this linked to higher rates of obesity, type 2 diabetes and cancer (Oduwole, Ladapo & Fajolu, 2012) and physical inactivity related NCDs are reported to be increasing (Olayinka, 2004).

Lifestyles characterized by adequate physical activity, nutrition, sleep, and no substance use help to maintain physical fitness, mental health and reduce the risk of non-communicable diseases (Shekhar et al., 2022). Moreover, universities represent a setting where students spend large amounts of time sitting, as measured by self-reports and accelerometry (Castro & Bennie, 2020; Paulus & Kunkel, 2021) and prolonged sitting promotes deconditioning (Quittan, 2016), which negatively affects students' abilities to meet the demands of increasingly physical workloads where El Ansari et al., (2020) and Wald et al., (2014), reports that large proportions of university students do not meet the current PA guidelines and sedentary behaviour recommendations, e.g., in Nigeria, Finland, the USA and the UK.

Whole body vibration and agility among sedentary population

The skill of displaying movements with as much great speed as possible is defined as the reaction given to a stimulant by the whole body in the shortest time possible by speedily changing direction (Sekulic, Spasic & Mirkov, 2017). In almost all sports branches, moving towards different directions in a speedy and sudden manner and then slowing down involve the movement of the whole body. In reality, being able to move to different directions in all types of sports is more important than the sprint speed from a straight line. Agility is one of the most important characteristics which have been developed in strength and fitness programs for athletes and which needs to be applied regularly (Sekulic et al., 2013). With the purpose of developing agility as required, both general and special training are made use of within a specific time period.

Agility, balance and coordination are three key factors for precise, rapid movements, and these three factors are affected by proprioception (Houglum, 2016) which was found to be impaired in patellofemoral pain (Powers, 2017). Training to improve proprioception can increase agility, quickness and acceleration in the performance of sports activities (Taskin & Bicer, 2015).

Whole body vibration and balance among sedentary population

On the other hand, balance impairment has been found in persons with patellofemoral pain, and given the obvious relationship between balance and agility; improvements in balance can contribute to improvements in agility because of strong direct relationships among agility, proprioception and balance (Acar & Eler 2019).

A common mechanism for WBV-induced enhancement of muscle activity is tonic vibration reflex (TVR) resulting from muscle spindle and α -motor neuron activation (Pollock &, Woledge, 2012;

Lienhard, 2015). WBV acts on neuromuscular coupling and improves motor coordination (Pollock & Woledge, 2012; Lienhard et al., 2015). Neural enhancement at the spinal level may underlie WBV-induced improvement in coordination, but neuromuscular activation enhancement causes and mechanisms have received minimal attention (Cochrane, 2011). Vibration activates muscle spindles, elicits alpha-motor neuron excitation and induces enhanced muscle activation (Rittweger, 2010). Vibration training affects the neuromuscular system and may have positive acute and chronic effects on neuromuscular activation (Wang & Chen, 2014; Tankisheva et al., 2015).

Physical inactivity and deficits in functional ability have been identified as independent contributors to falls among older adults (Uusi-Rasi, Patil & Karinkanta, 2017). Even though they are critical risk factors on sedentary lifestyle, they are modifiable and preventable through exercises (Benichou & Lord, 2016; Toraman, 2010). Balance is the base of all movements. There is a constant loss and recovery of balance during movement. Although balance is generally thought of as a static process, it is a highly integrated dynamic process that involves many neurological ways. In order to maintain body position during an action, acceleration and deceleration, during sudden location and direction changes, there is a need for balance (Nebahat, 2019). Balance is required in the performance of a large number of motor tasks. It is known that the balance, which defined as the “ability to apply movements at a speed as high as possible” affects the agility. Improvement of balance, including speed and explosive power, is considered to be one of the main features of agility improvement (Hakan, 2019).

Whole body vibration and gait of sedentary population

Previous studies have reported that WBV training can improve balance through several mechanisms, including the modulation of the excitability of the spinal Moto neuronal pool (Kipp

et al., 2011), the activation of motor units (Pang et al., 2006), and improved proprioception (Fontana et al., 2005). The WBV platform generates vertical oscillations and horizontal movements. The contact surface of the platform transmits vibration stimuli from the feet to the rest of the body (Yang et al., 2015). WBV therapy is thought to activate the Ia and II afferent fibers (Nardone et al., 2001) and tonic vibration reflexes by detecting the stretch of the muscle (Fontana et al., 2005). The effects can improve postural control and thus enhance proprioceptive function. These neuromuscular responses have been associated with improvements in the muscular strength and power of the lower extremities, flexibility, gait speed, and balance, as well as reduced pain and risk of falls (Cochrane, 2011).

Exercise training is an established non-pharmacological intervention for improving gait performance in older adults, including patients with dementia (Kemoun et al., 2010; Schwenk et al., 2014). Aerobic training (AT), resistance training (RT), and balance training have been shown to improve gait parameters, such as gait speed and stride length (Kao, 2018; Kemoun et al., 2010; Schwenk et al., 2014). A meta-analysis and systematic review revealed that RT with gradually increasing intensity, functional mobility training such as walking, or combination of various exercise modality are effective for improving gait speed or performance on the timed up and go test (TUG) in older adults (Kokkinos et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2019). Whole-body vibration (WBV) therapy has recently been investigated as a rehabilitation method for athletes and patients. It has been increasingly used in clinical practice for improving neuro-motor performance in various patient populations. Mechanical vibration at different frequencies and intensities has been widely used to improve muscle function and performance (Martinez et al., 2013). The vibration signals activate the muscle spindles, inducing reflexive activation of motor units (Pang et al., 2006). Thus, WBV training may reduce disability by improving balance, gait performance,

and mobility in stroke patients. However, although several studies have demonstrated the effects of WBV therapy on the functional recovery of the lower extremities to be more effective when applied at an early stage. Thus, we hypothesized that early WBV training would be more effective in improving balance and gait (Yang et al., 2015).

Regular training is especially important with regard to balance and gait, which is an important part of physical well-being, daily mobility and therefore general ability to function in everyday life (Fuchs, 2018). This is consistent with improved neuromuscular control leading to a better postural stability achieved through WBV training (Fort & Romero, 2012). Furthermore, good postural stability has a positive influence on balance and gaits (Romero et al., 2012). As recently demonstrated, vibration can improve balance and gaits in older people (Zhang, 2014), as well as in individuals with metabolic syndrome (Paineiras-Domingos, 2018), preventing falls and injuries (Da Cunha Sá-Caputo, 2018).

Whole body vibration (WBV) is a mechanical stimulus that has oscillatory motion and was hypothesized to enhance neuromuscular stimuli (Marin & Rhea; Marin, 2010).

Whole body vibration, injury rehabilitation and athletic performance among sedentary population

WBV, which was originally a therapeutic modality, was used to treat certain diseases (Claerbout et al., 2012) and for injury rehabilitation (Ebid & Ahmed, 2012). As early as the 1890s, studies were conducted on using WBV for improving some conditions of the human body (Bissonnette et al., 2010). Since WBV can be used with several vibration parameters e.g. frequency, amplitude, duration, body position, and type of vibration vertically or in an oscillating manner, previous studies reported varying results (Osawa, Oguma & Ishii, 2013; Rittweger, 2010). In recent years,

there has been an increased interest in the use of whole body vibration (WBV) to increase athletic performance, but also as it relates to sedentary people or recreational athletes (Colson et al., 2010; Pojskic & Pagaduan, 2015; Ritzmann et al., 2014). The potential benefits suggest that WBV could be a practical warm-up before exercise (Avelar & Costa, 2012).

Whole body vibration and body organs of sedentary population

Yang & Wang, (2014); Alvarez-Barbosa et al., (2019) and Rahimi et al., (2020), asserted that Whole Body Vibration Training has been shown to have positive effects on all organs of the human body, such as improving strength, balance, functional mobility, quality of life, reducing oxygen intake, as well as increasing blood flow and body fat percentage, bone mineral density, cardiopulmonary function, and vascular function in the older adults. Furthermore, it is done on a special platform and it is a frequently used exercise modality employed in fitness and health centres for the purpose of increasing muscle strength and balance (Machado et al., 2010; Sitjà-Rabert et al., 2012 & Petit et al., 2010).

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